

Balancing Performance and Memory: Investigating Compression Trade-offs for Stream Aggregates

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ABSTRACT

Stream Aggregates are crucial in distributed data analysis applications that summarize sensor data into valuable insights. Stream Processing Engines can deploy stream Aggregates across the edge-to-cloud spectrum. The heterogeneous hardware of said spectrum, though, introduces a need for optimizing performance and memory consumption trade-offs.

For stream Aggregates, state-of-the-art approaches can meet this challenge through memory compression applied to Aggregates' states, which consist of *windows* containing raw records, intermediate results, and metadata spanning a portion of the input. However, said approaches do not explore the impact of different compression techniques and focus on fixed-target compression strategies. To provide finer-grained control, we present preliminary results about the trade-offs between various compression libraries and introduce an adaptive compression mechanism that dynamically adjusts based on workload characteristics, providing insights into how to optimize memory compression for stream Aggregates while maintaining high processing performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

The stream processing paradigm has become the standard approach for big data pipelines extracting insights from continuous data sources in digital systems (e.g., vehicular networks and smart grids). To reduce and condense data, stream Aggregates enable data summarization over *windows* that analysts can define to specify which portions of recent events are relevant and how frequently to produce aggregated results.

Stream Processing Engines (SPEs) – the platforms executing streaming applications – can deploy Aggregates in data pipelines spanning the edge-to-cloud spectrum. This capability is crucial when pushing analysis to the edge rather than gathering data to the cloud to ensure scalable/efficient processing. However, when stream Aggregates are deployed at the edge on hardware-limited or shared devices, tuning the trade-offs of resource utilization, particularly memory, and performance is key. This is particularly so when for an Aggregate, over time, only some of its windows are frequently

accessed. In such a case, less-frequently accessed windows could be compressed. While this would introduce additional latency due to compression/decompression overheads, it would also reduce memory usage, making the trade-off potentially beneficial. Recent solutions investigating the use of memory compression on Aggregates' windows show promising results, but overlook the impact of different compression strategies. Also, existing approaches rely on fixed-target compression based on parameters potentially hard for analysts to configure, requiring deep pre-deployment knowledge of data characteristics, which analysts may not know.

Based on these observations, we present preliminary results studying the impact of different compression protocols and introduce a novel dynamic compression strategy for analysts to tune compression with limited prior knowledge of the characteristics of the data processed by an Aggregate.

Structure: Section 2 covers preliminaries, Section 3 study goals and approach, Section 4 our case study, Section 5 related work, and Section 6 conclusions. Our code is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20466468>.

2 PRELIMINARIES

2.1 Stream processing/stream Aggregates

A *Stream S* is an unbounded sequence of tuples. Each tuple t carries a timestamp $t.\tau$ and a payload $t.\phi$ (see [7]). An SPE executes *queries* composed of *sources*, *operators*, and *sinks*. Sources inject tuples representing real-time events such as sensor readings into the system. Operators arranged in graphs process/transform such tuples before passing results to sinks, which store or forward them to other applications. Operators are *stateless* - producing outputs from individual tuples - or *stateful*, with computations based on an evolving state accumulated from multiple tuples.

The Aggregate is a key stateful operator SPEs [1, 2, 4] provide to summarize input streams over *time-based windows* (simply windows). An Aggregate A is defined by:

Window Advance (WA), Window Size (WS): defining the event time intervals $[\ell WA, \ell WA + WS]$ covered by A , where $\ell \in \mathbb{N}$ and each interval is a window *instance* γ . If

$WA < WS$, the windows are *sliding*, and individual tuples can contribute to multiple overlapping window instances; if $WA = WS$, the windows do not overlap and are termed *tumbling*; if $WA > WS$, the windows are *jumping*, and some tuples may not be assigned to a window instance.

Function $f_K(t)$ (optional): which enables partitioned processing by grouping tuples sharing a common key into independent window instances to facilitate per-key aggregation.

Function $f_{add}(\gamma, t)$ to add the contribution of an input tuple t to the window instance γ .

Function $f_{out}(\gamma)$ to generate an output tuple t_o encapsulating the aggregated result from the window instance γ .

Function $f_{rm}(\gamma, t)$ (optional) to remove input tuple t 's contribution from the window instance γ .

The f_{rm} is optional because an Aggregate A may maintain, for each key, parallel window instances covering overlapping portions of time (i.e., for sliding windows) until their outputs are produced, and discard them afterward [9].

When a tuple t_o is output from window instance γ with a start time $\gamma.l$, $t_o.\tau$ is set to $\gamma.l + WS - \delta$ to indicate the latest event time observable in γ , where δ represents the granularity of event time progression for the SPE running A .

For timely and correct results, operators maintain *watermarks* to track the minimum event time that can still be observed in future tuples. An Aggregate A updates its watermark W_A^ω at wallclock time ω based on the latest watermark received from its input streams [12]. Sources emit watermarks as special tuples with increasing timestamps to signal event time advancement [1]. When W_A^ω increases, A emits results for all window instances $\gamma | \gamma.l + WS \leq W_A^\omega$, since no additional tuples will contribute to these windows, and propagates W_A^ω to its downstream peers.

2.2 State compression in stream Aggregates

We build upon prior work [11] for our compression algorithm. The algorithm selectively compresses the window instances of an Aggregate A based on the event time elapsed since their last update, based on a single parameter $D \in [0, +\infty]$ that defines the minimum event time distance, between a window's latest update and the latest processed tuple, required to trigger compression. When this distance exceeds D , γ is compressed. If $D = 0$, all window instances are compressed immediately after each update, maximizing memory efficiency at the cost of frequent compression/decompression overhead. Conversely, $D = +\infty$ disables compression, preserving instant access to the window state. Since A 's windows do not span more than WS event time units under steady watermark progression, a $D \geq WS$ effectively prevents any window instance from being compressed. We refer to [11] for a detailed explanation of the algorithm.

3 STUDY GOALS AND APPROACH

We build on the baseline algorithm from [11], which, for an Aggregate having only some of its windows accessed frequently, allows infrequently accessed windows to be compressed, saving memory at the cost of added latency. We investigate two key aspects. To account for different data compression techniques and their trade-offs, we study the impact of diverse libraries on the proposed solution's performance. Also, since choosing the right D can require analysts to have prior knowledge of data properties they might not possess, we propose an alternative that does not require choosing D (as we further elaborate in Section 4) but rather:

- a metric of interest to steer compression decisions, along with the periodicity P with which it should be checked, expressed either as a measure of time or processed tuples,
- a desired range $[m, M]$ for the selected metric, and
- actions A_m and A_M to adjust D when the metric falls below m or grows above M , respectively.

Then, the Aggregate continuously adjusts D based on real-time observations (see Figure 1, and Algorithms 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Dynamic D adjustments are potentially applied every P time units or processed tuples, through A_m if the monitored metric falls below threshold m or A_M if it grows above threshold M .

Algorithm 1: Dynamic D adjustment algorithm (P expressed as wallclock time)

Local Variables:

- 1 $lastDUdate$ // time of last check/update of D , initially null

Auxiliary Methods:

- 2 $getMetricOfInterest()$ // retrieve metric based on which D is checked/updated
- 3 $getSystemTime()$ // Retrieve the current wallclock time

Method $process(t)$

- 5 **if** $getSystemTime() - lastDUdate \geq P$ **then**
- 6 $s \leftarrow getMetricOfInterest();$
- 7 **if** $s \neq null \wedge s < m$ **then** $D \leftarrow A_m(D)$;
- 8 **if** $s \neq null \wedge s > M$ **then** $D \leftarrow A_M(D)$;
- 9 $lastDUdate \leftarrow getSystemTime();$
- 10 // Rest of algorithm from [11] follows

Algorithm 2: Dynamic D adjustment algorithm (P expressed as tuples)

Local Variables:

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1  $p \leftarrow P$  // tuples left before next check/update of  $D$ ,
   initialized to  $P$ 
Auxiliary Methods:
2 getMetricOfInterest () // retrieve metric based on
   which  $D$  is checked/updated
3 getSystemTime () // Retrieve the current wallclock time
4 Method process( $t$ )
5    $p \leftarrow p - 1$ ;
6   if  $p = 0$  then
7      $s \leftarrow$  getMetricOfInterest();
8     if  $s \neq \text{null} \wedge s < m$  then  $D \leftarrow A_m(D)$  ;
9     if  $s \neq \text{null} \wedge s > M$  then  $D \leftarrow A_M(D)$  ;
10     $p \leftarrow P$ ;
11    // Rest of algorithm from [11] follows

```

Our approach allows analysts to express what the compression should achieve (the desired metric behavior) rather than how it can achieve it (the proper D values).

To ensure a fair comparison with prior work, we evaluate our approach using the same state-of-the-art baseline and performance metrics, which include:

- **Throughput:** the tuples processed per second (t/s).
- **Latency:** the time from when a tuple t is fed to an A until the results triggered with t are output, in seconds (s).
- **Non-compressed/compressed (n/c) ratio:** the portion of non-compressed window instances over the overall ones maintained by the Aggregate.
- **Memory usage:** The memory (GB) used by A 's state.

Additionally, we rely on the **windows** metric (the overall number of window instances maintained by an A), which we include to better explain other metrics' trends. In this initial study, we assume that an analyst focused on compressing an A 's state aims to steer compression actions based on a single metric: the n/c ratio. Note, though, that, as mentioned in Section 6, future work can study multi-objective adjustments that account for multiple metrics at the same time.

4 USE CASE AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

In this preliminary study, we rely on the same data and use case investigating memory compression in [11]. More specifically, we use data from the Linear Road [8] simulated real-time traffic monitoring system. This dataset defines a stream of reports detailing vehicles' positions and speeds, with new reports generated every second. Consecutive reports from each vehicle are spaced 30 seconds apart (in event time). Each vehicle begins and ends reporting within a specified event time interval, lasting anywhere from a few minutes to tens of minutes. The simulated traffic spans 3 hours (in event time) and results in approximately 44 million tuples.

The Aggregate under investigation counts the per-vehicle stops. Each stop is a sequence of at least one position report with zero speed occurring between reports with non-zero speed (or at the very beginning or end of the journey). WA and WS are set to 2 and 20 minutes, respectively.

The experiments study varying injection rates: 5×10^3 , 10×10^3 , 20×10^3 , 33×10^3 , 50×10^3 , 100×10^3 , and 200×10^3 t/s, the latter representing the maximum rate sustainable by an Aggregate that does not compress its γ s. D values range from 0 to 10 minutes. We limit the max D value to 10 minutes since we observed in our experiments that higher values lead to almost no compression, with no actual compression once D is set to 20 minutes (i.e., when $D = WS$, see Section 2).

We evaluate three different compression techniques: *Snappy* [5], based on the LZ77 algorithm, and designed for high speed and reasonable compression rather than maximum compression efficiency, *Zstandard (Zstd)* [6], which offers a compression ratio comparable to that of Zlib but with significantly higher performance, and *JZlib* [3], a pure Java re-implementation of Zlib, which also relies on a variant of LZ77. By evaluating these different approaches, we aim to understand their impact on memory usage and processing efficiency within our stream Aggregate framework.

The experiments run for at least 10 minutes, excluding the data from the first minute (warm-up) and the last seconds (cool-down), on a single server with an Intel Xeon E5-2637 v4@3.50GHz with 4 cores, 8 threads, and 64 GB RAM. As discussed in [11], this server is suitable for edge deployments, a realistic scenario for our use case. Our code is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20466468>.

Compression Libraries' impact on Performance. We first study how the chosen libraries impact the throughput, latency, n/c ratio, and memory usage metrics. Results are shown in Figure 2, which consists of three columns, corresponding to the Snappy, Zstd, and JZlib libraries, and one row for each different metric. Within each plot, different lines (distinguished by color and pattern) represent different data injection rates. X-axis ticks are spaced evenly to better illustrate how the metrics evolve with varying D values.

In line with previous results [11], the higher the compression, the higher the performance degradation, with a more pronounced impact for higher injection rates. Both Snappy and Zstd outperform JZlib across all metrics, except for the n/c ratio, which is the same for all libraries due to the D values being fixed in these experiments. Comparing Snappy and Zstd, we observe that Zstd achieves lower throughput and higher latency but provides better compression efficiency.

To further analyze these trade-offs, Figure 3 presents the Snappy-to-Zstd ratio for throughput, latency, and memory utilization. As shown, at high injection rates and low D values (i.e., higher compression levels), Snappy achieves up to

Figure 2: Throughput, latency, n/c ratio, and memory metrics for the different compression libraries and increasing injection rates when D grows from 0 to 600 seconds.

twice the throughput of Zstd while halving latency, but at the cost of approximately 60% higher memory utilization.

By examining Figures 2 and 3, we observe distinct trends across all metrics, compression libraries, and injection rates when D decreases below 30 seconds. As explained in [11], this is because vehicles report data every 30 seconds. Hence, when D is less than 30 seconds, most window instances for actively reporting vehicles start being compressed. As observed, the n/c ratio increases from 0 to 1, but not linearly. Instead, it rises sharply when D exceeds ~ 15 seconds. This observation is further explored in the next experiment.

Dynamic Adjustments of D . We now consider the perspective of an analyst with limited knowledge of the data fed to the Aggregate: one who can observe the incoming data volume and who holds an estimate of the ratio of vehicles actively moving over those that have moved during the last 20 minutes, equal to approximately $\frac{1}{3}$, but who does not know the exact number of vehicles nor their reporting periodicity. Using the algorithm from Section 3, the analyst sets a target n/c ratio within $m = 0.3$ and $M = 0.4$, a P value of 10×10^3 tuples, A_m and A_M to increase and decrease D by 1 second, respectively, and uses the Snappy compression library. To stress-test the experiment, we allow dynamic adjustments of D while periodically resetting it to 0 and 30 seconds for every

3×10^6 input tuples. This alternation forces periodic shifts between maximum and more easily sustainable compression.

Results are shown in Figure 4, which consists of three columns representing different sustained throughputs and four rows showing the overall windows maintained by the Aggregate and how the n/c ratio, latency, and memory usage evolve during a 10-minute-long excerpt of the experiment. Vertical lines indicate when D is reset to 0 or 30 seconds.

Downward and upward spikes occur when D is reset to 0 and 30 seconds, respectively. These spikes are narrower at higher throughput levels. Nonetheless, regardless of the fluctuations' direction/magnitude, the algorithm consistently stabilizes the n/c ratio within the $[0.3, 0.4]$ target range.

As expected, latency and memory show the same trend of the increasing number of windows (because the keys maintained by the Aggregate and its output tuples increase over time) and also exhibit oscillations when D is reset. Variations in latency are less pronounced than those in memory, but both remain minor in magnitude. Latency fluctuations are quickly absorbed, with a negligible impact.

Comparing latency and memory metrics for dynamic versus fixed D further confirms that dynamic adaptations have negligible cost. For a fixed D of 15 seconds – resulting in an n/c ratio of approximately 0.35, the only fixed D within

Figure 3: Throughput, latency, and memory metrics ratio for Snappy over Zstd, for increasing injection rates and D values from 0 to 600 seconds.

[0.3, 0.4] in the experiments assessing the impact of different compression libraries – we observe latency and memory values of 1.2s and 0.14GB, 1.6s and 0.2GB, and 2.2s and 0.25GB for injection rates of approximately 10×10^3 t/s, 20×10^3 t/s, and 30×10^3 t/s, respectively. For a varying D , the corresponding values for the same injection rates are 1.1s and 0.13GB, 1.5s and 0.19GB, and 2s and 0.25GB. Despite minor variations due to the dynamic D within the target n/c ratio interval, the observed values remain very close to those of the fixed case, reinforcing the dynamic adaptation’s negligible costs.

5 RELATED WORK

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work proposing threshold-based self-adaptive compression of stream Aggregates’ internal state (i.e., the window instances; see Section 2). The closest related work, which we build upon, is [11]. However, the algorithm proposed in [11] employs a static D value and does not consider adaptive adjustments over time.

Another relevant study is [13], which focuses on compression techniques that enable direct operations on compressed data without requiring decompression. This approach prioritizes memory efficiency at the cost of performance and represents a complementary direction for future work.

Expanding the scope to memory compression applied to other components of streaming applications, we find research applying compression to streams rather than on the states maintained by stateful operators [15, 16], or on the states persisted to disk for fault-tolerance purposes [14].

Additionally, other works explore compression techniques tailored for specialized hardware like FPGAs [10]. These approaches are complementary, addressing e.g., different aspects of stream Aggregates, like tuple-based windows.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In cloud-to-edge data pipelines, efficient edge-based analysis is becoming a necessary alternative to centralized data gathering and pure cloud-based processing. In this evolving landscape, lean and adaptive streaming analytics are key. Stream Aggregates, a fundamental component in such applications, have long been supported by distributed and parallel SPEs. However, the challenge of tuning the trade-offs of performance and resource efficiency – particularly memory consumption – has only recently gained attention.

We presented our preliminary findings to improve a recent compression technique introduced in [11], exploring the impact of different compression libraries and proposing a self-adaptive approach that moves beyond fixed-target compression toward a dynamically adjustable strategy.

Our initial results quantify the trade-offs of different compression libraries between performance and compression efficiency. Some prioritize throughput and latency at the expense of reduced compression levels, while others focus on maximizing compression with greater performance overhead. The measured differences can be substantial, especially when compression is to be maximized and the computational load of an Aggregate is high. As such, adjusting the chosen compression library during the execution of an Aggregate should be further investigated. Also, dynamic compression adjustments can have negligible costs, enhancing the usability and flexibility of streaming analytics. Further research can also focus on *multi-objective* dynamic adaptations of the desired compression levels, where compression decisions are based on multiple metrics simultaneously rather than a single threshold. Exploring how different system statistics influence adaptive compression could lead to more intelligent and responsive algorithms. Another avenue for future work is the integration of *lossy compression* or compression that allows *direct operations on compressed data without decompression*, which, while supporting an efficient use of memory, may introduce trade-offs in analytical accuracy.

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Figure 4: Evolution of windows, n/c ratio, latency, and memory metrics over time for increasing throughput values, with dynamic D adjustments targeting range $[0.3, 0.4]$ for the n/c ratio and D reset to 0 or 30 (alternatively) every 3×10^6 processed tuples. Vertical lines show when such resetting is applied.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Accessed:2025-02-14. Apache Flink. <https://flink.apache.org>.
- [2] Accessed:2025-02-14. Apache Storm. <http://storm.apache.org>.
- [3] Accessed:2025-02-14. JZlib. <https://github.com/yymnk/jzlib>.
- [4] Accessed:2025-02-14. Liebre SPE. <https://github.com/vincenzogulisano/Liebre>.
- [5] Accessed:2025-02-14. Snappy. <https://github.com/xerial/snappy-java>.
- [6] Accessed:2025-02-14. Zstandard. <https://facebook.github.io/zstd/>.
- [7] Tyler Akidau, Robert Bradshaw, Craig Chambers, Slava Chernyak, Rafael J Fernández-Moctezuma, Reuven Lax, Sam McVeety, Daniel Mills, Frances Perry, Eric Schmidt, and Sam Wittle. 2015. The dataflow model: a practical approach to balancing correctness, latency, and cost in massive-scale, unbounded, out-of-order data processing. *Proc. Endowment* 8, 12 (2015), 1792–1803.
- [8] Arvind Arasu, Mitch Cherniack, Eduardo Galvez, David Maier, Anurag S Maskey, Esther Ryzkina, Michael Stonebraker, and Richard Tibbetts. 2004. Linear road: a stream data management benchmark. In *Proc. of the Thirtieth Int'l Conf. on Very large data bases-Volume 30*. VLDB Endowment, 480–491.
- [9] Prajith Ramakrishnan Geethakumari, Vincenzo Gulisano, Pedro Trancoso, and Ioannis Sourdis. 2019. Time-swad: A dataflow engine for time-based single window stream aggregation. In *2019 International Conference on Field-Programmable Technology (ICFPT)*. IEEE, 72–80.
- [10] Prajith Ramakrishnan Geethakumari and Ioannis Sourdis. 2023. Stream Aggregation with Compressed Sliding-Windows. *ACM Transactions on Reconfigurable Technology and Systems* (2023).
- [11] Vincenzo Gulisano. 2023. An Algorithm for Tunable Memory Compression of Time-Based Windows for Stream Aggregates. In *European Conference on Parallel Processing*. Springer, 18–29.
- [12] Vincenzo Gulisano, Dimitris Palyvos-Giannas, Bastian Havers, and Marina Papatriantafidou. 2020. The role of event-time order in data streaming analysis. In *Proceedings of the 14th ACM International Conference on Distributed and Event-based Systems*. 214–217.
- [13] Gennady Pekhimenko, Chuanxiong Guo, Myeongjae Jeon, Peng Huang, and Lidong Zhou. 2018. Tersecades: Efficient data compression in stream processing. In *2018 USENIX Annual Technical Conference (USENIX ATC 18)*. 307–320.
- [14] Georgios Theodorakis, Fotios Kounelis, Peter Pietzuch, and Holger Pirk. 2021. Scabbard: Single-node fault-tolerant stream processing. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 15, 2 (2021), 361–374.
- [15] Xianzhi Zeng and Shuhao Zhang. 2023. Parallelizing Stream Compression for IoT Applications on Asymmetric Multicores. In *2023 IEEE 39th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)*. 950–964. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDE55515.2023.00078>
- [16] Yu Zhang, Feng Zhang, Hourun Li, Shuhao Zhang, and Xiaoyong Du. 2023. CompressStreamDB: Fine-Grained Adaptive Stream Processing without Decompression. In *2023 IEEE 39th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)*. 408–422. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDE55515.2023.00038>